

THE
HAHNIIDAE
OF
SOUTH
AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

The family Hahniidae is a small family known from 23 genera. Only one genus *Hahnia* C.L. Koch, 1841 is known from South Africa represented by eight species of which seven are endemic to South Africa. Only one species *Hahnia schubotzi* Strand, 1913 was not previously listed from South Africa. The African fauna was last revised by Bosmans (1981). Six of the species are listed as Least Concern and two species are data deficient.

TABLE OF CONTENT

HAHNIIDAE	4
• <i>Hahnia abrahami</i> (Hewitt, 1915) *	5
• <i>Hahnia clathrata</i> Simon, 1898 *	6
• <i>Hahnia larseni</i> Marusik, 2017 *	7
• <i>Hahnia laticeps</i> Simon, 1898 *	8
• <i>Hahnia lobata</i> Bosmans, 1981 *	9
• <i>Hahnia schubotzi</i> Strand, 1913	10
• <i>Hahnia tabulicola</i> Simon, 1898 *	11-12
• <i>Hahnia zodarioides</i> (Simon, 1898) *	13
REFERENCES	14

* SPECIES LISTED IN WSC (2020) FOR SOUTH AFRICA

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FAMILY HAHNIIDAE Bertkau, 1878

The family Hahniidae has a worldwide distribution and is represented by 23 genera (World Spider Catalog (2020)).

COMMON NAMES: Comb-Tailed Spiders

MORPHOLOGY: Small (3-6 mm), three-clawed, ecribellate, entelegyne, eight-eyed spiders; tracheal spiracles open midway on abdomen; spinnerets situated in a transverse row. Carapace longer than wide; narrowed in cephalic region; fovea short with striae; sternum truncated anteriorly; posterior apex narrowing to a point; eyes eight; in two rows (4:4); equal in size; eye rows slightly procurved; chelicerae with two teeth on each side of cheliceral furrow; lateral side of chelicerae with series of ridges more strongly developed in males (stridulating organ); mouthparts labium wider than long. Legs short, robust, with few setae; three claws. Abdomen oval; spinnerets in a single transverse row; posterior spinnerets long, two-segmented; colulus paired; respiratory system two booklungs; tracheal spiracle midway between genital opening and base of spinnerets (Bosmans 1981).

LIFESTYLE: Hahniids make their small sheet-webs in crevices and depressions like hoof prints on the soil surface or on tree trunks. In the early morning their delicate webs become visible when dew collects on them. The spider hangs beneath the web and when disturbed disappears in the vegetation or beneath sand particles. Stridulatory organs are present on their chelicerae composed of a series of ridges on the lateral side of the chelicerae completed by the spur on the palpal patella. It is stronger developed in the males (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué 1997; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014).

TAXONOMY: Not recently revised.

Hahniidae. a: *Hahnia* sp., female, dorsolateral view; b: line-drawing showing leg lengths' c: abdomen ventral view, showing spinnerets arranged in a single row; d: male palp, dorsal view; e: epigyne. (After Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué 1997).

GENUS *HAHNIA* C. L. Koch, 1841

The genus *Hahnia* described by C.L.Koch (1841) is represented by 102 species (WSC 2020) and eight species are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Hahnia Comb-Tailed Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Hahnia pusilla* C. L. Koch, 1841

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: <6 mm, males similar in size to females. Colour: carapace pale yellow-brown to dark brown with dark markings, margined with black; abdomen: usually with a double row of oblique creamy chevron markings on a dark grey background. Carapace longer than wide; narrower in the cephalic region; with short fovea and distinct striae; eight eyes in two rows (4:4); eyes equal in size and arranged in two procurved rows. Abdomen oval; spinnerets in a single transverse row with the posterior spinnerets long and two-segmented. Legs short, robust, with few setae (Bosmans 1980, 1981).

LIFESTYLE: Hahniids make delicate sheet-webs. They hide beneath grains of soil at the edge of the web. They have been collected in damp places such as the base of shrubs near water, in moss growing on tree trunks, under stones, wet caves, or from the leaf litter of trees and shrubs in dense and open forests, savannas and grasslands. In the early morning their delicate webs become visible when dew collects on them. The spider hangs beneath the web and when disturbed, disappears into the vegetation or beneath sand particles. Stridulatory organs composed of a series of ridges on the lateral side of the chelicerae, and a spur on the palpal patella are present. It is stronger developed in males than in females (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2010, 2013; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2013).

TAXONOMY: Revised by Bosmans (1986).

Hahnia sp. male Photo Linda Wiese

Hahnia sp. spinnerets Photo ASD

Hahnia sp. in Wynberg caves iSpot

Hahnia abrahami (Hewitt, 1915)

COMMON NAME: Abraham's Comb-Tailed Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Hewitt (1915) as *Muizenbergia abrahami* from Muizenberg. It is presently known only from three coastal localities (EOO= 55 km²; AOO=12 km²; 6-198 m a.s.l.). Two of the records were sampled prior to 1915, the third specimen was collected from Hermanus more recently (2008). Too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. More sampling is needed, to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient.

LIFE STYLE: The species was sampled while searching for *Desis*, in the interspaces of the calcareous masses built up by marine annelids. These might be littoral spiders or a derivative of the South African terrestrial fauna. The Hermanus specimen was sampled from a coastal dune.

DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape*: Muizenberg (-34.1, 18.47); Hermanus (Brekfiskaai) (-34.4, 19.25); St. James (-34.11, 18.46).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling is needed to determine the species range. As a littoral species, oil spills and sea pollution may be a threat.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Bosmans (1992). Known from both sexes.

Hahnia abrahami male after Hewitt (1915)

12
Hahnia abrahami epigynum after Bosmans (1992)

Hahnia clathrata Simon, 1898

COMMON NAME: Cape Comb-Tailed Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Simon (1898) with the type locality given only as "Prom. Bonae Spei". The species is also recorded from Namibia. In South Africa it is known from four provinces, including ten protected areas (EOO=317 537km²; AOO= 72 km²; 39-1698 m a.s.l.). Although identification of the male is still problematic, the female was sampled over a wide range. Due to its wide geographic range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species makes small sheet-webs in litter. Sampled from the Fynbos, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Fort Fordyce Nature Reserve (-32.605, 26.388); King William's Town (-32.88, 27.39); Storms River Forest Station (-33.95, 23.83); Thomas Baines Nature Reserve (-33.41, 26.5); Tsitsikamma National Park (-34.017, 23.878). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66). **Mpumalanga:** Graskop, 30 km N (-24.93, 30.84). **Western Cape:** Brenton-on-Sea (-34.1, 23.03); Table Mountain National Park (Cape of Good Hope Nature Reserve, Olifantsbos near Skaife Centre) (-34.24, 18.41); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Hermanus (Fisherhaven) (-34.47, 19.27); Marloth Nature Reserve (-34.25, 20.57); Cape Point Nature Reserve (-34.19, 18.42); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Crystal Pools, Wupperthal (-32.35, 19.14); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Driehoek (-32.42, 19.16); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneeu-kop (-32.36, 19.16); Karoo Desert National Botanical Garden (-33.61, 19.46); Stellenbosch, Demorgenzon (-33.936, 18.750).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in ten protected areas such as Opathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015); De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009) and Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016). More sampling is needed to collect the male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Bosmans (1986). . Known only from the female.

Epigynum after Bosmans (1981)

Hahnia clathrata female Photo ASD

Hahnia larseni Marusik, 2017

COMMON NAME: Larsen's Comb-Tailed Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Marusik (2017) from the Karoo National Botanical Gardens. It is known only from six specimens sampled at the type locality (EOO= 4 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 322 m a.s.l.). Too little is known about the habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. More sampling is needed, to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient.

LIFE STYLE: Sampled from litter under bushes in the Fynbos Biome (Marusik 2017)..

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Karoo Desert National Botanical Garden (-33.61,19.46).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in Karoo Desert National Botanical Garden. More sampling is needed to determine the species range. As this species distribution is yet to be determined the threats are still unknown, however if it occurs more widely in the Breede River Valley it may be threatened by habitat loss as a result of vineyard cultivation and urban development.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Marusik 2017).

Hahnia larseni female after Marusik (2017)

Palp after Marusik (2017)

Hahnia laticeps Simon, 1898

COMMON NAME: Simonstown Comb-Tailed Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Simon (1898) from Simonstown in the Western Cape. The species is known from three provinces including four protected areas (EOO= 186 809 km²; AOO= 56 km²; 39-2985 m a.s.l.). Numerous specimens were recently sampled on the Sani Pass in the Drakensberg. Although only known from one sex the species has a wide range therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species makes small sheet-webs in litter in the Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013) and Fynbos biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mpofu Nature Reserve (-32.606, 26.597); Thyspunt, 12 km WNW, Cape St Francis (-34.206, 24.708). **KwaZulu-Natal :** Sani Pass 900m altitude (-30.185, 30.149); Sani Pass 1500m altitude (-29.650,29.451); Sani Pass 1800m altitude (-29.620, 29.422); Sani Pass 2100m altitude (-29.601,29.324);Sani Pass 2400m altitude (-29.603, 29.313); Sani Pass 2700m altitude (-29.588, 29.293); Sani Pass 3000m altitude(-29.600,29.291). **Western Cape:** Brenton-on-Sea (-34.1, 23.03); Cape of Good Hope Nature Reserve (-34.24, 18.41); Marloth Nature Reserve (-34.25, 20.57); Simonstown (-34.19, 18.42); Fisherhaven, Hermanus District (-34.47, 19.27); Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve (-34.32, 18.96).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in four protected areas but more sampling is needed to collect the male and determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female

Epigynum after Bosmans (1981)

Hahnia laticeps female Photo ASD

Hahnia lobata Bosmans, 1981

COMMON NAME: Bosman's Comb-Tailed Spider.

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Bosmans (1981) from type locality only given as "Cap de Bonne Espérance". It is known from two provinces, including five protected areas (EOO= 241 300 km²; AOO= 32 km²; 24-1498 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Species makes small sheet-webs in litter and was also collected from forest litter, pine plantations and caves in the Fynbos, Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes. The species was commonly found at the Ngome State Forest where more than 650 specimens were sampled with pitfall traps also from pine forest at Ngome (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Ndumo Game Reserve (Nyamiti Pan) (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Greater St Lucia Wetland Park (-29.29, 26.27); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Good Hope Plantation, Boston (-29.651, 29.976); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Eastern Shores Nature Reserve (-29.095, 32.157); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, St Lucia (-29.29, 26.27); Ndumo Game Reserve, Nyamiti Pan (-26.544, 32.155); Wakefield Farm (-29.473, 29.893). **Western Cape:** Wynberg Caves (-34.05, 18.45); Blouberg (-33.01, 18.01).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in five protected areas. More sampling is needed to collect the female.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the male.

Palp after Bosmans (1981)

Hahnia laticeps female from Blouberg Photo Peter Webb

Hahnia schubotzi Strand, 1913

COMMON NAME: Schubotz's Comb-Tailed Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Strand (1913) from Rwanda. It is known from four African countries. In South Africa it is presently known from two provinces (EOO= 7 403 km²; AOO=12 km²; 103-1557 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range in Africa it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species makes small sheet-webs in litter. It was sampled from the Savanna and Fynbos biomes as well as in apple orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Rwanda, Tanzania, Kenya and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Mpumalanga:* Bergvliet Forest Station (-25.10, 30.78); Machadodorp (-25.66,30.26). *Western Cape:* Stellenbosch (-33.93,18.85)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Bergvliet Forest Station. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Bosmans (1986). Known from both sexes.

Epigynum after Bosmans (1982)

Palp after Bosmans (1982)

Hahnia tabulicola Simon, 1898

COMMON NAME: Common Comb-Tailed Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Simon (1898) from South Africa with type locality as "Prom. Bonae Spei". It is recorded from seven African countries. The species is commonly found throughout South Africa (EOO=611 358 km²; AOO= 176 km²; 4-2892 m a.s.l.) and has been recorded from seven provinces, and is found in more than 10 protected areas. Due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species makes small sheet-webs in litter and has been collected using pitfall traps. It was sampled from all the floral biomes except the Thicket and Desert biomes (Haddad et al. 2013; Foord et al. 2011). It was also sampled from cotton and maize (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Cameroon, Democratic Republic of Congo, Kenya, Malawi, Tanzania and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Prentjiesberg (-31.18, 28.28); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Asante Sana Private Game Reserve, Waterkloof (-32.283, 24.939); Asante Sana Private Game Reserve, Zuurkloof (-32.267, 25.004); Fort Fordyce Nature Reserve (-32.605, 26.388); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.05, 24.9167); King William's Town (-32.88, 27.39); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Tsitsikamma National Park(-34.017, 23.878); Zuurberg Pass (-33.32, 25.68). **Free State:** Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); National Botanical Gardens Bloemfontein (-29.05, 26.21); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Platberg Nature Reserve (-28.27, 29.2). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Garden Castle (-29.75, 29.2); Drakensberg Mountain Range Monk's Cowl (-24.62,30.88); Giant's Castle Nature Reserve (-29.23, 29.48); Kamberg Nature Reserve (-29.39, 29.67); Loteni Nature Reserve (-29.47, 29.52); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1). Dukuduku Forest.-28.309, 32.368); Sani Pass 900m alt. (-30.2,30.4); Sani Pass 2100m altitude (-29.601, 29.324); Sani Pass 2400m alt. (-29.66, 29.51); Sani Pass 2700m altitude (-29.588, 29.293); Vryheid (-27.77, 30.79). **Limpo-po:** Grootbosch Forest (-23.73, 30.03); Hanglip Forest (-23.04, 29.91); Lajuma Mountain Retreat (-23.03, 29.45); Potgietersrus/Mokopane (-24.17, 29.00); Roodewal Forest (-23.02, 30.03); Sovenga Hill (-24.17, 29); Thathe Vondo Forest (-22.83, 30.27); Springbok Flats: Tuinplaas (-24.56, 28.46); Bekendevelei (-24.52, 28.51); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve

Epigynum after Bosmans (1981)

Palp after Bosmans (1981)

Hahnia tabulicola male and female Photo CH

Hahnia tabulicola Simon, 1898

Mpumalanga: Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29); Carolina, Farm Grootpan (-26.06,30.11); God's Window (-24.874, 30.891); Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87); Sabie, Lone Creek Falls (-25.1, 30.78); Graskop (-24.93, 30.84). **North West:** Babelegi (-25.39, 28.28). **Western Cape:** Brenton-on-Sea (-34.10, 23.03); De Hoop Nature Reserve: Back Dunes (-34.45, 20.44); Potberg (-34.45, 20.44); Cape Hartenbos (-34.12, 22.10)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following areas: De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009); Asante Sana Private Game Reserve, Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016); Witteberg Nature Reserve; Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Bosmans (1981). Known from both sexes.

Hahnia tabulicola male and female from the Free State Photo Allen Jones

Hahnia zodarioides Simon, 1898

COMMON NAME: Cederberg Comb-Tailed Spider.

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Simon (1898) as *Scotussa zodarioides* with type locality given as Cape of Good Hope. It is known from two provinces (EOO= 62 923 km²; AOO= 88 km²; 9-1755 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographic range, the species is listed as of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species makes small sheet-webs in litter. It has been collected using pitfall traps in the Fynbos biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Western Cape: Lambert's Bay, 15 m a.s.l. (-32.18, 18.31); Lambert's Bay, 10 m a.s.l. (-23.18, 18.32); Lambert's Bay, 7 m a.s.l. (-32.17, 18.32); Lambert's Bay, 4 m a.s.l. (-32.18, 18.32); Aan Het Berg, 251m a.s.l. (-32.28, 18.53); Sawadee, 359 m a.s.l. (-32.34, 18.99); Niewoudt's Pass, 527 m a.s.l. (-32.35, 19.01); Cederberg Wilderness Area, 643 m a.s.l. (-32.4, 19.09); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Driehoek, 918 mm a.s.l. (-32.42, 19.17); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Driehoek, 919 mm a.s.l. (-32.42, 19.16); Cederberg Wilderness Area, 1152 m a.s.l. (-32.46, 19.24); Cederberg Wilderness Area 8.1 1325 m a.s.l. (-32.43, 19.22); Cederberg Wilderness Area, 1337 m a.s.l. (-32.43, 18.21); Cederberg Wilderness Area, 1366 m a.s.l. (-32.43, 19.21); Cederberg Wilderness Area 9.1, 1544 m a.s.l. (-32.39, 19.15); Sneekop 10.1, 1605 m a.s.l. (-32.36, 19.15); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop (-32.36, 19.17); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop, 1881 m a.s.l. (-32.35, 19.16); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop, 1919 m a.s.l. (-32.36, 19.16); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop, 1830 (-32.36, 19.16); Sneekop 12.1, CWA, 1702m (-32.35, 19.17); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop 13.1, 1557 (-32.35, 19.17); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop 13.2, 1557 m a.s.l. (-32.35, 18.17); Crystal Pools, Wupperthal, CWA, 1286 m a.s.l. (-32.35, 19.14); Crystal Pools, Wupperthal 1289 m a.s.l. (-32.34, 19.14); Crystal Pools 15.3, Wupperthal, 1133 m a.s.l. (-32.33, 18.14); Crystal Pools 15.4, Wupperthal, 1133 m a.s.l. (-32.33, 18.15); Wupperthal, 522 m a.s.l. (-32.28, 19.22); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in several protected areas in the Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016), Asante Sana Private Game Reserve, Witteberg Nature Reserve and Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Bosmans (1992).. Known only from female. The male has been sampled but still undescribed,

Palp undescribed male
Photo ASD

Epigynum after Bosmans (1992)

Hahnia zodarioides female and male Photo ASD

REFERENCES

- BOSMANS R. 1981. Études sur les Hahniidae (Araneae) africains II. Les espèces du genre *Hahnia* de la collection Simon. *Bulletin du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle de Paris* (4) 3(A1): 203-211.
- BOSMANS, R. 1986. Studies on African Hahniidae (Araneae) IV. Redescription of *Hahnia schubotzi* Strand and remarks on its synonymy, with description of three new species. *Entomologica Scandinavica* 17: 339-349
- BOSMANS, R. 1992. Spiders of the family Hahniidae from Sulawesi, Indonesia with remarks on synonymy and zoogeography (Arachnida: Araneae: Hahniidae). *Belgian Journal of Zoology* 122: 83-91
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A. S., HADDAD C. R., FOORD S. H., LYLE R., LOTZ L. N., HELBERG L., MATHEBULA S., VAN DEN BERG A., VAN DEN BERG A. M., VAN NIEKERK E. AND JOCQUÉ R. 2010. First Atlas of the Spiders of South Africa. South African National Survey of Arachnida. *SANSA Technical Report version 1* (2010): 1158 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A. S. 2014. *Field Guide of the Spiders of South Africa*. Lapa Publisher 424 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A. S. 2020. Spider of the Table Mountain National Park. SANSA Final Report 14 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. AND MYBURGH, J.G. 2009. A review of the cave spider spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) from South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 64(1): 53-61 .
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & HADDAD C.R. 2014. *Spiders of the Grassland Biome*. Plant Protection Handbook no 19, Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria, 120 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., FOORD S.H. & HADDAD C.R. 2013. *Spiders of the Savanna Biome*. University of Venda & Agricultural Research Council.
- HADDAD, C.R. AND DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2009. The Arachnida of the De Hoop Nature Reserve in the Western Cape. *Koedoe* 51(1): 1-9.
- FOORD S. H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. AND HADDAD C.R. 2011. The *faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Savanna Biome in South Africa*. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 66: 170-201.
- FOORD, S. AND DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2016. The effect of elevation and time on mountain spider diversity: a view of two aspects in the Cederberg mountains of South Africa. *Journal of Biogeography* 43, 2354–236 .
- HADDAD, C.R. AND DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., 2015. Diversity of non-acarine arachnids of the Ophathe Game Reserve, South Africa: Testing a rapid sampling protocol. *Koedoe* 57(1), Art. #1255, 15 pages.
- HADDAD, C.R. AND DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2009. A checklist of the non-acarine arachnids (Chelicerata: Arachnida) of the De Hoop Nature Reserve, Western Cape Province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 51(1): 1-9.
- HADDAD, C.R. AND DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., 2015. Diversity of non-acarine arachnids of the Ophathe Game Reserve, South Africa: Testing a rapid sampling protocol. *Koedoe* 57(1), Art. #1255, 15 pages. [http:// dx.doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v57i1.1255](http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v57i1.1255).
- LEHTINEN, P. T. 1967. Classification of the cribellate spiders and some allied families, with notes on the evolution of the suborder Araneomorpha. *Annales Zoologici Fennici* 4: 199-468.
- MARUSIK, Y.M. 2017. On two sibling species of *Hahnia* (Araneae: Hahniidae) from Western Cape, South Africa. *Arachnology* 17 (6), 299-301.
- SIMON E. 1898. Descriptions d'arachnides nouveaux des familles des Agelenidae, Pisauridae, Lycosidae et Oxyopidae. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* 42: 1-34.
- SIMON, E. 1898. Histoire naturelle des araignées. Paris 2, 193-380.
- STRAND, E. 1913. *Arachnida*. I. In: Schubotz, H. (ed.) *Wissenschaftliche Ergebnisse der Deutschen Zentral-Afrika-Expedition 1907-1908, unter Führung Adolf Friedrichs, Herzogs zu Mecklenburg*. Klinkhardt and Biermann, Leipzig. 4 (Zool. 2), 325-474.
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG 2020. World Spider Catalog. Version 21.0. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on 10 June 2020 doi: 10.24436/2